

Thoughts on actual scientific problems of drawing geometry and drawing.

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Annotation: *In order to renew the old one of any craft, technique and technology, and to create a new one, if there is a drawing of it first, a project is created. It is known that orthogonal projection, right-angle projection method is the most convenient method for solving problems with small differences from each other; drawing drawings.*

Keywords: *In the topics, our encyclopedic scholars who lived in the territory of Central Asia, Muhammad al-Khorazmi, Ahmad Farghani, Abu Nasr Farobai, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, etc., were engaged in the graphic sciences described in their works on astronomy, geodesy, optics, and geometry. it would be appropriate to provide information.*

The development of the technique depends on the development of drawing geometry and engineering graphics on a world scale. Science, technology and science are the most important aspects of development. Special geometry, in the words of Gospar Monj, "Drawing is the language of technology", "Drawing geometry is the grammar of this language." The role of engineering graphics is extremely important for learning and mastering all general engineering and engineering subjects.

Therefore, the disciplines of visual arts, drawing geometry and engineering graphics are inextricably linked. We believe that it is appropriate to provide high-level knowledge of these subjects not only in technical universities, but also in vocational colleges, academic lyceums and general education schools. An axonometric projection of each object, detail, that is, a clear image, develops the spatial understanding of the future specialist, develops the ability to visualize and imagine. If axonometric projections, that is, drawings, are carried out in close connection with technical painting, if they are studied, the thinking of the pupil or student deepens and develops. In general education schools, it is appropriate to use the right-angle projection methods in drawing and drawing together with the subjects of fine arts and painting, to study the axonometric views of objects or details, details in the direction of mechanical engineering, and the names of objects. In colleges of agriculture and national economy, drawing geometry and drawing sciences, i.e. starting from geometric departments, mechanical engineering department, drawings of kinematic and electrical schemes, conventional signs should be studied more deeply.

The role of technology in the development of agriculture and national economy is very important. It is our important task to train specialists in all developments, that is, in connection with the use of modern technology and due to the fact that the equipment, mechanisms, machines, devices brought from abroad are being used in practice. In connection with the use of new technologies, all the knowledge learned in the drawing geometry and drawing sciences and the use of computer programs to work on drawings related to the earth's surface, that is, the use of a new technology system, will deepen the knowledge of the student and student. Using a computer is one of the effective ways for students to improve their knowledge.

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The student learns to work out all the problems in sketch geometry, drawing and drawing clear images of details using axonometric projection methods. They will have information about studying world technology and technological methods of world standards and drawings. Due to the lack of methodological, educational manuals and textbooks, literature in Latin alphabet for students according to the needs of the times, their creation is a current topic.

The growth of science and technology in our independent homeland requires that we teach the above-mentioned subjects in depth among the main subjects so that our future young specialists can work in all fields and reach the heights of science. Therefore, it would be appropriate to increase the number of hours allocated to drawing geometry and engineering graphics in all technical educational institutions, including higher educational institutions in the field of engineering.

Al-Farabi (870-950), a great encyclopedic scientist who lived in the Middle Ages, offers simple methods of making a paraboloid that allows the use of solar energy and records how much power it has. If we are going to make a mirror that burns an object at a distance using the sun's rays, we must first make a model that creates the mirror.

We will conduct a circle for this. Its radius is equal to the distance between the "item" we want to burn. Let this circle be AVS. We pass its ADS diameter. We measure and place the same sections on the line SD starting from point S. The smaller the incisions, the clearer and better the lekalo. Let these sections be CF, FH, HG, GE and ED. Through points D, E, G, H and F, we draw lines at right angles to SD and continue them to points B, I, K, L and M on both sides. We connect points S and V, S and I, S and K, S and L, S and M (1. 1).

Cross section SM is equal to cross section FN is equal to CL Cross section HX is equal to cross section SK Cross section GO is equal to CI Cross section EP is equal to cross section SV We make DS. We connect the points S, N, X, O and S and form a line along this line. Then we make a mirror out of metal, such as iron, bronze, copper or tin, and polish it until it shines. If the mirror is crooked, we fix it with the help of a level so that the point S coincides with the center of the level. If the lekalo falls on top of the glass, we will have a burning glass with a high burning power. The second method of making a lekalo for a burning window. If we want to make it, we get an arbitrary distance. Let us assume that half of it is the section AV and continue it in its direction. We place the line DV perpendicular to the line SV from point V and continue it on both sides. On the line VS, we measure the small lines VE, EG, GH and HC (1.2).

We bisect AE at point F and draw a circle with radius FA centered at point F. It intersects the line VD at points J. We draw parallel lines from points J to line AS, and parallel lines from point E to VD and form points L. After that, we divide the line AG at the point M and draw a circle with the radius MA with the center at the point M. It crosses the line VD at N points. We draw a line NX from N points until a point X parallel to the line AS is formed.

Now. We bisect AN at point O and draw a circle with radius OA centered at point O. It intersects the line VD at points R. From points R, parallel to the line VS, we draw a line PZ until the point Z is formed. We connect the points B, L, X and Z with the help of a curve to form a plane. If it is necessary to check the mirror, its point V should be placed in front of the mirror. In this way, we create an incendiary glass with a large burning capacity (O.U. Mavlonov, co-op. M.A. Mirkhanova, co-op., Bukhara OO and ESTI). Literature: 1. Al-Farabi Mathematical treatise "Science" Alma-Ata 1972

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Literature:

1. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Palaces of the Timurid Period of the middle Ages of Uzbekistan. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(2), 24-28.
2. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2022). Palaces In The Historical Cities Of Uzbekistan Formation. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12, 15-18.
3. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Analytical Research Work on the Palaces of the Timurids in the Medieval Period of Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(3), 7-10.
4. Sabohat, M., &Firuza, M. (2022). Periods of Formation of Historical Structures of Architecture with Geometric Shapes. *Journal of Architectural Design*, 4, 21-26.
5. Eshatov, I. Q., Mavlonov, M. D., &Mahmudova, F. (2022). Analysis of Placement of Agromomatic Levels of Commercial Services in Jizak City Structure. *Journal of Architectural Design*, 5, 6-11.
6. Bakhromovna, K. Z., & Ibraimovna, M. F. (2022). Use of Modern Industrial Technologies in Architecture.
7. Hidirov, M. M., Eshatov, I. Q., &Mahmudova, F. (2021, June). ARCHITECTURAL AND PLANNING ORGANIZATION OF AGGLOMERATIONAL TRADE AND SERVICE COMPLEXES IN THE UZBEKISTAN. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 60-64).
8. Ibraimovna, M. F. Abdusattorovna, M. S. (2023). Analytical Research Work on the Palaces of the Timurids in the Medieval Period of Uzbekistan. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(3), 7-10.
9. FiruzaIbraimovna, M. (2023). Scientific and Natural Study of the Architecture of the Khiva Garden-Palaces, Development of Recommendations for their Use for Modern Tourism Purposes. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 10-13.
10. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Analysis of Various Roofs and Roofs. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(3), 33-39.
11. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Khiva is an Open-Air City-Museum. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(4), 36-39.
12. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). History of Khiva. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(4), 8-12.
13. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Experiences of Restoring Palaces in Historical Cities of Uzbekistan and Historical Parks Around Them. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(3), 41-44.
14. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Formation of Palaces in Uzbekistan in the Late Middle Ages-Khanate Period. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(3), 33-36.
15. Ibraimovna, M. F. (2023). Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(5), 10-14.
16. Makhmudova, F. (2023). DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE. STUDY AND CALCULATION OF SPATIAL BLOCKS WITH A CYLINDRICAL COATING SHELL. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(10), 163-166.
17. Abdirasulovna, M. N. (2023). Some Questions about Structural Schemes of Buildings. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(4), 1-6.